

Fire light Soccer2D Simulation Team Description Paper 2024

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Abstract

This article contains explanations about the activities of fire light. This year, our 2D football simulation team has tried to improve the quality of its main functions and have a proper defense and attack plan. We developed our ideas with design and algorithms, some of these algorithms and solutions are given here.

keywords: Robocup ·Soccer 2D simulation ·Conditional decision · Machine learning.

1. Introduction

This article contains explanations about the activities of fire light This year's 2D football simulation team, our team tried to put potential effects on the team. Match offensive and defensive strategies to get your ideas Algorithm design and development Here we mention some of these algorithms And solutions.

2. Current Scientific Focus

Our team is trying to implement changes in the development of the algorithm of the defense and attack plan. So that we have a more complete defensive wall in different situations. To have more scoring opportunities, you should attack from the corner of the field. This strategy and algorithm is under development.

3. Defence

3.1 Location_pos

By using punctuation our goal is to determine the correct formation of defense and attack for the players. In these defense coordinates, the player has a compact arrangement when the opponent has the ball to get the ball easily, and a more discrete arrangement when attacking to create a good attacking position. Also, for times like foul, corner, out, etc., according to the coordinates of the ball, a separate arrangement has been defined so that with the correct coordinates and the formation of a wall from the player, they can create good situations.

3.2 Approach

1. Position of our player.

2. Position of the opponent.

3. Position of the ball Our defense works like a rocket, when the opposition players attack us with the ball and come forward, one of our players facing the opposition tries to clear the ball well and return to his position, players 2 , 3, 4, 5.and 6 are our main defense, although player 6 is the driver and does both midfield and ball exchange. When the ball goes up the field, the defensive players face the ball.Our goal is not for the ball to reach our goal. In the basic code, we created a rectangle with positioning for defense, but the possibility of dispersion was very high,and with missile defense, we have reduced the possibility of error.

4. Offence

4.1 Shoot

Our shoot is based on artificial intelligence that uses genetic algorithm. Our team is the first student team that used the genetic algorithm. In this algorithm, by combining genetic codes, safe points in the opponent's gate are randomly selected, and the code itself does this without our intervention by forming a new population and genetic functions. By getting the best points, scoring is done from the valuation function and taking into account the conditions in the football game, such as the absence of the opponent, etc., and the point in the goal that has a higher score is hit.

4.2 Pass

Our pass algorithm and function is different and it knows the attacking formation and the player number, first it makes a comment around the player and draws a hypothesis and we get the number of opponents in one point, if the number of opponent players gathered in one point is small and insignificant. By examining conditions such as the lack of movement of the opponent when reaching the ball, a short distance and a more suitable position, the pass is approached, otherwise the answer is deep (far pass) to confuse the opponent.

< Check the position of the opponent player to pass >

4.3 Dribble

Our dribble follows a law :

When the coordinates of the player and the ball are the same and the opponent is in front of us, just like when the player moves forward, he directs the ball under the opponent with a kick and uses the opponent's surprise. Passes the ball and dribbles. This code has the ability to surprise the opponent's player at the moment when he takes the ball from the opponent and dribbles.

< Dribbling players >

4.3 Press

Our pass algorithm is divided into three parts, first of all the main pass which normally selects the best and closest teammate. The second is the deep pass that is reserved for our defensive players to get the ball away from our goal sooner. At the end, you pass forward and hit the ball to a safe point that is far from the opponent, so that my closest teammate moves forward and owns the ball.

4.Conclusion

During this short period of time, using our conditions and limited time, many changes such as:

- 1.saving time
- 2.A composition suitable for the world
- 3.Optimal shot test and safe pass

5. References

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